

Religious tourism objects and their classification

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Tourism is one of the largest sectors of the world economy, it occupies an important place in the structure of the national economy of many countries, and for some it forms the basis of international specialization, population employment and well-being. The development of tourism infrastructure, transport networks, competition between industry enterprises, gradual growth of incomes and living standards of the population in most of the developing countries, globalization trends in the international community allow further expansion of international tourist flows.

According to linguists, the historical roots of the word "tourism" go back to the Latin *tornus*, which means "circular movement" [20; p. 73]. The word "tour", which means "travel" in French, was transferred to English in the 18th century, on the basis of which English words such as "tourist" and "tourism" appeared. In the early years of the 19th century, the corresponding English words entered the French language and appeared in explanatory dictionaries of the French language. Then, by the end of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century, the word tourism entered all the main European languages, especially Russian, through French and English. In Russian language encyclopedias, encyclopedic and explanatory dictionaries, scientific and journalistic works, the words "tourism" and "tourist" were widely used in the 1930-40s [20; p. 76]. So, at the present time, the words "tourism" and "tourist" are among the international terms, and are widely used, including in the Uzbek language. The concepts of "tourism" and "tourist" are defined differently in different scientific and legal sources. The first scientific definition of the term "tourism" was given in 1830 by the French scientist V. Jackmo. According to him, "tourism is a journey that ends with returning to the place from where it started" [80; p. 269].

Later, for many years, world science and education used the definition given in the book "Essays on the General Theory of Tourism" published in 1942 by Swiss scientists W. Hunsicker and K. Krapf. According to him, tourism is a way for people to go to areas where they do not have permanent residences and spend time there without having to work and earn money [39; p. 53].

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Tourism" defines the concept of "tourism" as follows: "Tourism is the right of an individual to visit a place (country) for health, educational, professional or other purposes from the place of permanent residence. it is understood that he leaves (travels) for a period of one year without engaging in paid activities" [2].

In the opinion of the first expert from the CIS geographers to defend a doctorate thesis on tourism, the famous Kazakh geographer SR Yerdavletov, the term "tourism" refers to people traveling to an area other than their permanent residence (with the condition of return) for at least 24 hours and at most 6 months. used for leisure or travel purposes [21; p. 300].

Russian geographer A.Yu. Aleksandrova defined tourism as follows: Tourism is relations and events that occur during the migration and stay of people in places other than the place of permanent residence and work" [73; pp. 10-11].

Kyrgyz scientist A.G. Nizamiyev focuses on 4 aspects of this process [24; p. 5-6; 25; pp. 7-10]:

1. Tourism is a trip of a person to a different area from his usual living environment;
2. This process does not exceed 12 months continuously and must return to the starting place;
3. The consumer nature of the trip, that is, not earning material benefits during the trip and only spending money;
4. Prioritization of activities related to spending free time.

Based on the above-mentioned points, in our opinion, the main characteristics of tourism as a type of activity are that people are outside their permanent place of residence, the duration of the trip does not exceed 1 year and return to the original place, it is related to meaningful spending of free time, and visitors it can be considered that it consists in not engaging in activities that bring money. It should be noted that in current conditions, tourism should be understood not only as the activities of tourists, but also as a separate branch of the economy that provides special services to them.

Among the types of tourism, religious tourism stands out. In the scientific research of the geographical aspects of the development of religious tourism, foreign geographers, in particular, A.V. Babkin [75], K. Griffin [53], R. Raj [53], GN Gujina [18], H. Okhavat [64], T.A. The contribution of Prokopenko [86], TTXristov [94] and others is significant.

According to TT Hristov, religious tourism is the pilgrimage of representatives of different religions [94; p. 337].

Yu.S. Putrik defined religious tourism as follows: "Religious tourism is travel for educational purposes, educational tourism related to visiting holy places and religions for the purpose of getting to know educational centers, including religious temples in the form of excursions, historical and travel to natural, religious institutions and places" [87; p. 256].

Therefore, religious tourism means Therefore, religious tourism should be understood as a trip related to visiting religious objects.

Specialists according to [75; pp. 40-41, 86; p. 191], religious tourism the following species own into takes :

1. Pilgrimage tourism ;
2. Religious excursion tourism ;
3. Religious scientific research tourism .

Religious of tourism this views of travelers goals with mutually differs . In particular , pilgrimage tourism religious of people internal emotions , emotions because of holy to places visit order and this through his own spiritual desire Satisfied , religious feelings expression to do mean holds Pilgrims holy steps and to shrines visit to order inviter one how much spiritual circumstances separate can